

University Sports: Comparison of All India Inter-University Achievements of Panjab University Men and Women Teams

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Anju Lata
Associate Professor
Physical Education
Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV
College For Women
Chandigarh, Punjab, India

Rubina Sharma
Assistant Professor
Physical Education
Mehr Chand Mahajan DAV
College For Women
Chandigarh, Punjab, India

Abstract

The aim of the study is to analyse the difference between the performance level of men and women from Panjab University at All India inter-university games from 1993 to 2016 (23 years). The study includes six disciplines: hockey, football, basketball, softball, handball, and volleyball. To serve the purpose, a t-test was utilized. The divulge hypotheses, is tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the performance levels between men and women in the games of hockey, basketball, softball, handball, and volleyball. However, a significant difference was observed in the game of football. The study also projects the total number of championships, where overall, men showed dominance in football, basketball, handball, and softball, while women has also demonstrated notable achievements in softball, hockey, softball, basketball, handball, and football.

Keywords All India Inter-university, Panjab University, Men and Women Performance, Competition, Sports.

Introduction

Sports as a model of human creativity is a form of physical activity which encourages, arouse, develop and faster one's physical and mental potential. In form of competitions, intense physical and mental efforts are done to obtain victory and performance.

In Indian system of sports and physical education, university plays an important role. The university sports are considered as the backbone of sports competition all over the world. The first Inter-University tournament was organised in 1940-41, that begins with men's tournament only. The disciplines in which competition were organised were Athletics, Hockey, and Tennis. In 1928, the "Inter-University Athletic Board" was formed with the approval of Inter-University Board. In 1940-41, in the category of women on tennis competition was conducted.

To improve and encourage the University sports, the Maulana Abdul Kalam Trophy (MAKA) was introduced in 1956-57. Firstly, it was won by "Bombay University". It is a rolling trophy awarded to the overall top performing university in sports of the preceding year to arouse keen interest among students and to motivate various teams to take up competitive sports.

Aim of study

Inter-university competitions are very essential to prepare the youth for various international competitions like world university, commonwealth games, Asian games and Olympic games. Keeping in view the importance of university sports the following objectives are set-

1. To compare men and women performance of Panjab university Chandigarh teams.
2. To analyse the sports achievements of men and women category.

3. To find out the best discipline in men and women category in Panjab university Chandigarh.

Review of Literature

In establishing hegemony of the British Empire, during Malta and Afghan wars, mostly Punjab Regiments took part and created a very favourable impression upon British officers, who were dealing with all affairs of governance. This impression paid favourable dividends on the proposal for considering the elevation of Panjab University college into university. The oriental teaching system of Panjab University college was so strong in its constituent institutes that nobody afforded to mislay its teaching functions in lieu of its elevation to become only the examining body. Though it faced many hassles and the process of the bill took long time to become an Act, yet finally the Panjab University Bill was presented and passed in the legislative council at Shimla on 5th October, 1882 (Appendix 9). The approval act XIX of 1882 to establish and incorporate the university of Panjab was given by the Indian office at London on 25th January 1882.

From 1941 till date the Panjab University has given hundreds of International and National achievers in various competitions under men and women category. The Panjab University has won MAKATROPHY 15 times since its inception.

S.No.	Year	Name of University
1.	1957-58	Panjab University
2.	1958-59	Panjab University
3.	1960-61	Panjab University
4.	1961-62	Panjab University
5.	1967-68	Panjab University
6.	1968-69	Panjab University
7.	1969-70	Panjab University
8.	1970-71	Panjab University
9.	1971-72	Panjab University
10.	1994-95	Panjab University
11.	1995-96	Panjab University
12.	2004-05	Panjab University
13.	2018-19	Panjab University
14.	2019-20	Panjab University
15.	2020-2021	Panjab University

Modified from Source: New Horizon, A. Lata, 2020, p. 250.

Table 1: MAKATROPHY Winner List (Panjab University)

Methodology

The current study is an analysis of sports performance of men and women teams at All India Inter-university competitions. Data has been collected from 1993-2016, with the view to consider the performance at Inter-university level. The data has been obtained from Annual report book of Panjab University sports council and minutes of meetings of

various committees of the university. Only top 4 positions were taken into consideration. The data has been collected from following games-

- i. Hockey
- ii. Football
- iii. Basketball
- iv. Handball
- v. Softball
- vi. Volleyball

Statistics Used in the Study

To determine the difference between performance of Panjab University men and women on various games from 1993-2016, descriptive and inferential statistics have been applied. To check the Homoscedasticity, Levene's test has been implemented. To check the normality of the data, Skewness and Kurtosis have been performed. According to Byrne (2010); Hair, Black, Babin, and Anderson (2010), the data is considered to be normal if skewness is between -2 to +2 and Kurtosis is between -7 to +7. Further, to find out the difference between the performance of Panjab University men and women among various games at All India University, t-test has been utilized. The divulge hypotheses, would be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Analysis

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances ^{a, b}					
		Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
Hockey	Based on Mean	0.07	1	44	0.78
Football	Based on Mean	4.70	1	44	0.36
Basketball	Based on Mean	0.38	1	44	0.54
Softball	Based on Mean	2.95	1	44	0.09
Handball	Based on Mean	2.30	1	44	0.13
Volleyball	Based on Mean	0.06	1	44	0.80

Source: Author's computation

Table 2: Levene's Test of equality

Table-2 shows the significance values of Levene's Statistics, based on the mean of all variables, ranging from 0.09 to 0.80, which is greater than 0.05. So, it is concluded that there is homoscedasticity.

MEN							
Games	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Hockey	23	.00	3.00	0.70	1.22	1.29	-0.17
Football	23	.00	4.00	0.60	1.07	2.00	4.15
Basketball	23	.00	4.00	1.35	1.49	0.68	-1.01
Softball	23	.00	3.00	0.91	1.24	0.80	-1.15
Handball	23	.00	3.00	1.04	1.26	0.65	-1.32
Volleyball	23	.00	4.00	0.74	1.48	1.68	1.14

Source: Author's computation

Table 3: Descriptive analysis of Hockey, Football, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball games of Panjab University men's performance at All India Inter-university from 1993-2016

The above table-3 describes the mean, standard deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Maximum and minimum values of performance of Panjab University men's teams at various All India Inter-university tournaments from 1993 to 2016. For hockey, the mean value is 0.70, with the standard deviation of 1.22. In the description of football, mean value is found to be 0.60, and it's standard deviation is 1.07. For basketball and softball, mean value are found as 1.35 and 0.91, with the standard deviation of 1.49 and 1.24 respectively. Similarly, for handball and volleyball, mean values are 1.04 and 0.74, with the standard deviation of 1.26 and 1.48 respectively. The values for skewness on the variables of hockey, football and volleyball depicts positive and highly skewed distribution ($Sk > 1$), 1.29, 2.00 and 1.68 respectively. For the values of basketball, softball and handball, Sk showcase as 0.68, 0.80 and 0.65, which represents positive and moderately skewed distribution. The above mention Kurtosis values on variable of hockey, basketball, softball and handball are -0.17, -1.01, -1.15 and -1.32 respectively. These curves are negative, as they are less than 0, therefore, representing platykurtic. On the other hand, the values of football and volleyball are 4.15 and 1.14. these values are positive, hence depicting leptokurtic curve.

In conclusion, we can say that the data is skewed and kurtotic, but does not differ significantly from normality (Byrne (2010); Hair et al. (2010)). Therefore, we can say that data is normally distributed in terms of Skewness and Kurtosis.

Figure 1: showcasing Mean values of Hockey, Football, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball games of Panjab University men's performance at All India Inter-university from 1993-2016

WOMEN

Games	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Hockey	23	.00	4.00	0.96	1.29	1.04	-0.22
Football	23	.00	4.00	0.96	1.46	1.13	-0.32
Basketball	23	.00	4.00	1.17	1.37	0.81	-0.52
Softball	23	.00	3.00	1.00	1.00	0.29	-1.42
Handball	23	.00	3.00	0.61	1.03	1.44	0.68
Volleyball	23	.00	4.00	0.70	1.46	1.83	1.67

Source: Author’s computation

Table 4: Descriptive analysis of Hockey, Football, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball games of Panjab University women’s performance at All India Inter-university from 1993-2016

Table-4 represents the mean, standard deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Maximum and minimum values of performance of Panjab University women’s teams at various All India Inter-university tournaments from 1993 to 2016. The mean values of hockey and football is 0.96 each, with the standard deviation of 1.29 and 1.46. For the description of basketball and softball, mean values are found to be 1.17 and 1, and their standard deviation is 1.37 and 1, respectively. Similarly, for handball and volleyball, mean values are 0.61 and 0.70, with the standard deviation of 1.03 and 1.44 respectively. The values for skewness on the variables of hockey, football, handball and volleyball depicts positive and highly skewed distribution ($Sk > 1$), 1.04, 1.13, 1.14 and 1.83 respectively. For the values of basketball, Sk showcase as 0.81, which represents positive and moderately skewed distribution. The value of softball, Sk depicts as 0.29, which represents positive and fairly skewed distribution. The above mention Kurtosis values on variable of hockey, football, basketball and softball are -0.22, -0.32, -0.52 and -1.42 respectively. These curves are negative, as they are less than 0, therefore, representing platykurtic. On the other hand, the values of handball and volleyball are 0.68 and 1.67, which are positive, hence depicting leptokurtic curve.

In conclusion, we can say that the data is skewed and kurtotic, but does not differ significantly from normality (Byrne (2010); Hair et al. (2010)). Therefore, we can say that data is normally distributed in terms of Skewness and Kurtosis.

Figure 2: Mean values of Hockey, Football, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball games of Panjab University men’s performance at All India Inter-university from 1993-2016

Independent 't' Test (Performance (1993-2016))

GAMES	MEN			WOMEN			t-value	df	p-value
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD			
Hockey	23	0.70	1.22	23	0.96	1.29	0.70	44	0.48
Football	23	0.61	1.07	23	0.96	1.46	0.91	44	0.03*
Basketball	23	1.35	1.49	23	1.17	1.37	-0.41	44	0.54
Softball	23	0.91	1.24	23	1.00	1.00	0.26	44	0.09
Handball	23	1.04	1.26	23	0.61	1.03	-1.27	44	0.13
Volleyball	23	0.74	1.48	23	0.70	1.46	-0.10	44	0.80

*Significant at 0.05 level

Source- Author's computation

Table 5: Comparison of means of Hockey, Football, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball games on the level of performance from 1993-2016

Table 5 showcase the comparison of means of men and women on the performance of Hockey, Football, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball games form 1993-2016. The t-values of Hockey, Basketball, Softball, Handball and Volleyball are 0.70, -0.41, 0.26, -1.27 and -0.10, which resulted in the p value of 0.48, 0.54, 0.09, 0.13 and 0.80, which is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), hence no significant difference was seen in the level of performance. The t-value of Football was found to be 0.91, which resulted in the p value of 0.03, which is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), hence depicting the significant difference between the performance of men and women.

Panjab University Championships (1993-2016)			
S.No.	GAME	MEN	WOMEN
1.	Hockey	0	3
2.	Football	5	1
3.	Basketball	4	3
4.	Softball	1	4
5.	Volleyball	0	1
6.	Handball	3	2

Table 6: showcasing the total number of championships of Panjab University men and women at All India Inter-university tournaments from 1993-2016

Table 6 describes the total number of championships of Panjab University men and women at All India Inter-university tournaments from 1993-2016. Men have won maximum number of championships in Football (5), followed by Basketball (4), Handball (3) and Softball (1). Similarly, women have won maximum number of championships in Softball (4), followed by Hockey & Basketball (3 each), Handball (2), Football & Volleyball (1 each).

Figure 3: Total number of Panjab University championships from 1993-2016 (Men)

Figure 4: Total number of Panjab University championships from 1993-2016 (Women)

Findings

H:01 Acknowledged that there would be no statistically significant difference between the performance level of men and women category at All India Inter-university level in hockey game. The result showcased no statistically significant difference, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. H:02 Affirmed that there would be no statistically significant difference between the performance level of men and women category at All India Inter-university level in football game. However, the achieved results showed a statistically significant difference, therefore at this point the hypothesis is rejected. H:03 States that there would be no statistically significant difference between the performance level of men and women category at All India Inter-university level in basketball game. The findings do not reveal any statistically significant difference, henceforth the hypothesis is accepted. H:04 Asserted that there would be no statistically significant difference between the performance level of men and women category at All India Inter-university level in softball game. The result demonstrated no statistically significant difference, at this point the hypothesis is accepted. H:05 Affirmed that there would be no statistically significant difference between the performance level of men and women category at All India Inter-university level in handball game. Therefore, the findings do not reveal any statistically significant difference, so the hypothesis is accepted. H:06 Acknowledged that there would be no statistically significant difference between the performance level of men and women category at All India Inter-university level in volleyball game. According to outcome of result, no statistically significant difference was showcased, henceforth, the hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

The Championships spanning from 1993 to 2016 (23 years) provided an exciting platform for athletes from Panjab University to engage in spirited competition across a wide range of sports. The men's team displayed their prowess in various disciplines, with football emerging as the most successful sport, capturing five championships. The football team showcased their tactical acumen, technical abilities, and teamwork to secure victories over the years. Basketball too, witnessed strong performance from the men's team, securing four championships through skilful shooting, strategic gameplay, and effective coordination on the court. Handball also managed to get three championships, while softball clinched one title. However, hockey, and volleyball did not yield any championships for the men's team during this period. On women's side softball emerged as a shining star, clinching four championships. The softball teams showcased a blend of power, precision, and strategy to outplay their opponents and secure decisive victories. The women's also showcased dominance in hockey and basketball, clinching three championships each, while handball seizes two titles. However, women's football, and volleyball teams only managed to achieve one championship each. Though these championships reflect dedication, discipline, and talent, of the athletes representing Panjab University, but to improve the number of championships, more emphasis should be given on enhanced training and coaching programs, integration of sports science and technology, talent identification and development. Furthermore, upgradation of infrastructure, fostering collaborating, and exchange programs can yield more fruitful results.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Same type of study can be done for other universities.
2. Same type of study can be done for individual sports/events
3. Same type of study can be done for school age groups.
4. Special coaching may be arranged for the games in which he performance is low
5. Special infrastructure/academies may be created for the games in which the performance is very good.

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